

IMPROVING THE TASKS OF CRIME PREVENTION

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Abstract: This article discusses the relevance of the research topic, concepts for improving crime prevention tasks, the current state and implementation characteristics of general, special, individual, and victimological prevention measures. Additionally, it presents an analysis of practical application of norms in organizing activities to improve crime prevention, the level of their practical implementation, as well as procedural documents and errors and shortcomings in this field.

Keywords: Crime prevention, sociological approach, psychological approach, legal approach, social assistance, rehabilitation system, education and legal culture, public safety, monitoring system, law enforcement agencies, security provision.

Offenses are one of the most pressing problems in society, posing a serious threat not only to the offenders themselves but also to the stability and security of society. Therefore, the crime prevention system should function effectively in all social spheres. Today, there are many measures aimed at preventing offenses, but there is a need for new, effective approaches and methodologies in this regard.

This article examines the theoretical foundations and practical ways to improve crime prevention tasks. Based on the noble idea of "Enlightenment against Ignorance" in the field of crime prevention and combating crime, it is of great importance to early identify and eliminate the causes and conditions for committing offenses of a religious-extremist nature in each mahalla, prevent errors and shortcomings in crime prevention, improve crime prevention tasks, and organize activities to implement measures. The state and its relevant bodies are established to ensure peace and stability in society, and most importantly, to protect the sacred human right to life from criminal encroachments.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Prevention of Offenses" defines the following as the main tasks of crime prevention:

- ensuring the protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of the individual;

- raising legal awareness and legal culture in society, strengthening legality;
- identifying, studying the causes of the commission of offenses and the conditions that allow them, taking measures to eliminate them;
- social rehabilitation and social adaptation of victims of offenses, persons prone to committing offenses, who have committed offenses, including previously convicted and released from places of deprivation of liberty;
- reducing the risk of individuals becoming victims of offenses;
- ensuring mutual cooperation and coordination of the activities of bodies and institutions that directly carry out and participate in crime prevention.

There are several approaches to analyzing the theoretical foundations of crime prevention. In particular, approaches from sociological, psychological, economic, and legal perspectives play an important role. Each of them plays a special role in improving the effectiveness of the crime prevention system.

Sociological approach: This approach links offenses to social factors. Factors such as the social status of the population, its income level, education and employment influence the occurrence of offenses. Therefore, reducing social inequality, improving education, and ensuring social justice in society can be the foundation for crime prevention.

The psychological approach: in the psychological approach, the internal motives, values, emotions, and psychological state of a person are considered the main reason for the occurrence of offenses. In this approach, it is important to ensure personal prevention and mental stability in society.

Legal approach: A legal approach is also important in the prevention of offenses. In this approach, it is important to protect the rights, strengthen administrative measures, and establish fair and effective penalties. The development of new legal norms and the improvement of existing ones can be effective in preventing offenses.

It should be noted that the system of crime prevention units of the internal affairs bodies includes:

- Department of Public Security of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Crime Prevention Service of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- Offenses prevention services of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Main Department of Internal Affairs of the city of Tashkent, regional internal affairs departments;
- Centers for providing social and legal assistance to minors of the internal affairs bodies;
- departments (divisions, groups) for the prevention of offenses of departments (divisions, groups) for the coordination of the activities of internal affairs bodies of districts (cities), ensuring public safety on transport;
- Structural structures such as support points in villages, auls and mahallas of the internal affairs bodies have been defined.

One of the most important tasks in the sphere is the organization of the prevention service in close cooperation with the population, citizens' self-government bodies and other civil society institutions, aiming this work, first of all, at ensuring early prevention of offenses, raising the legal culture in society, instilling in citizens respect for the law and an attitude of intolerance to any manifestation of violation of the law. The serious shortcomings and problems accumulated in the activities of law enforcement agencies in recent years hinder the effective implementation of these tasks.

In particular, work on the prevention and prevention of offenses is mainly focused on combating the consequences of unlawful acts committed, the work on early prevention of offenses, in-depth analysis, identification and elimination of the causes and conditions for their commission does not yield the expected results. Therefore, today, the most important task of law enforcement agencies in our country is not to fundamentally change the methods of organizing their activities, in particular, to expose cases of violations of the law and take measures, but to ensure early prevention and prevention of these cases.

Ways to improve the system of crime prevention:

Strengthening education and upbringing: Providing the new generation with legal knowledge, raising legal culture and teaching them to respect the law is one of the main directions of crime prevention. In this regard, educational programs and legal propaganda work play an important role.

- Development of social assistance and rehabilitation systems: The increase in offenses can be driven by factors such as social isolation, economic difficulties and domestic violence. Therefore, the development of social assistance and rehabilitation systems, as well as the provision of psychological and legal assistance to those facing difficulties, is of paramount importance in crime prevention.

- Improving surveillance and monitoring systems: Effective monitoring of crime prevention is necessary. Installing CCTV cameras, strengthening cooperation with the police and other law enforcement agencies, and increasing public safety will help make the prevention system more effective.

Taking into account economic factors: Economic crises can lead to an increase in crime. Therefore, ensuring economic stability, creating jobs, and improving the standard of living of the population play a significant role in preventing offenses.

- Improving the Penal System: It is necessary to develop personal rehabilitation and rehabilitation programs, not only considering punishments as physical punishment. Particular attention should be paid to the reintegration of the convicted person into society and their adaptation to social norms.

Crime prevention is a comprehensive and multifaceted process in which all segments of society, the state, law enforcement agencies, education and healthcare systems, and social services must work together. By implementing theoretical approaches in real practice, applying innovative methods, and creating effective monitoring systems to improve crime prevention tasks, it is possible to ensure public safety. Only through a comprehensive approach and effective systems can crime prevention in society be achieved.

Crime prevention plays a crucial role in ensuring the safety and stability of society. This process should be aimed not only at preventing offenses, but also at solving social, psychological, and economic problems. Since the causes of violations are large-scale and depend on many factors, the prevention system must also be multifaceted. The combination of social, psychological, and legal approaches contributes to the creation of an effective system for crime prevention.

Today, the main focus in crime prevention is not only on punishment, but also on improving society and creating advanced educational systems. Raising legal culture in society, expanding legal knowledge among the population, and explaining the consequences of offenses are important steps in preventing offenses. However, it is necessary not only to limit oneself to theoretical approaches, but also to effectively apply practical approaches. When considering social and economic factors as well as the causes of offenses, it is important to pay special attention to reducing social inequality, ensuring economic stability, and increasing youth employment.

Furthermore, establishing effective cooperation between law enforcement agencies and society, strengthening surveillance and monitoring systems, as

well as developing social assistance systems, will contribute to more effective crime prevention. Moreover, punishment should be effectively implemented not only in a physical form, but also through psychological rehabilitation, personality re-education, and reintegration into society.

This, in turn, will contribute to reducing crime and ensuring societal stability. A comprehensive approach to crime prevention, cooperation between the state and society, and the integration of legal and psychological support systems lead to a decrease in crime rates. Furthermore, an effective crime prevention system should be built encompassing all spheres of society, including education, healthcare, the economy, and law enforcement. Ensuring the safety of society means not only preventing offenses, but also ensuring security, justice, and peace in society. Therefore, the system of crime prevention requires comprehensive and innovative approaches in modern conditions. At the same time, to increase the effectiveness of crime prevention, it is necessary to improve relations between state bodies and the public, strengthen social assistance systems, and expand legal and psychological rehabilitation programs.

Summarizing the above, crime prevention is the primary means of maintaining a stable society and ensuring legal order. Only by working together in all areas, from every member of society to state bodies, can the prevention of offenses be achieved.

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